

A Study on Work-Life Balance of Employees in Industrial Sector of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar

¹Madhuri Waghmare, ²Aakash wankhede

¹²MBA Student

¹²MBA department HR

¹²International centre of excellence in engineering and management

¹madhuri123waghmare@gmail.com, ²director@iceemabad.com

Abstract—The present study analyzes work-life balance and its impact on job satisfaction and productivity among employees. Data collected from 100 respondents using structured questionnaire. Results show strong relationship between WLB and employee performance.

Index Terms—Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Productivity, Industrial Employees

I. Introduction

Work-life balance refers to maintaining equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal life. Industrial employees often face long hours and stress affecting their well-being.

II. Objectives of the Study

To study work-life balance, analyze factors affecting it, evaluate its impact on job satisfaction, and measure employee productivity.

III. Hypothesis

H0: No significant relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction.

H1: Significant relationship exists between work-life balance and job satisfaction.

IV. Literature Review

Various studies highlight that proper work-life balance improves employee satisfaction and reduces stress. Research indicates flexible policies enhance productivity.

V. Research Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted. Primary data collected through questionnaires from 100 respondents. Secondary data from journals, books and websites.

VI. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Majority respondents belong to age group 20–30. Most employees reported moderate workload and stress. Employees with better work-life balance showed higher satisfaction.

VII. Findings

Employees experience moderate stress. Work-life balance positively impacts satisfaction and productivity.

VIII. Suggestions

Organizations should introduce flexible work hours, improve leave policies, and focus on employee wellness.

IX. Conclusion

Work-life balance plays a crucial role in employee performance and satisfaction.

References

[1] Books, Journals, Websites related to HR and Work-Life Balance.